

The Complexity of Human Consciousness: A Phenomenological Approach Inspired by Sir Roger Penrose

Gargi Mukherjee

Research Scholar, Visva-Bharati Univ, Santi Niketan

Abstract: In this article, the author explores the nature of consciousness from a phenomenological perspective. She bases herself on the classic work of Roger Penrose on Artificial Intelligence and human consciousness *The Emperor's New Mind*, where he upholds that consciousness can be understood only from a new understanding of quantum mechanics. The complex consciousness that each one of us possesses makes us unique. It poses questions, questions about our own self, meaning, freedom and existence. The most marvellous thing is that it can raise questions about itself!

Keywords: Roger Penrose, Consciousness, Intentionality, Phenomenology, Quantum Mechanics, The Emperor's New Mind.

It was heartening to read that Sir Roger Penrose, alongside German Reinhard Genzel and American Andrea Ghez, won the prize for discoveries relating to black holes. The 89-year old Briton, a professor at Oxford University, proved with maths that the formation of black holes was possible, basing his work largely on Albert Einstein's general theory of relativity. Einstein did not believe that black holes really existed.

While wishing Sir Penrose all the best, in this essay, I want to discuss what he writes about consciousness. I have a keen interest in this topic

due to my background in phenomenology (Thomas, 2020). I have an added reason to write these few lines. At Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan, where I pursue my doctoral research, I know many companions who were deeply impressed by Penrose when he visited us in 1998 (Academia Europaea n.d.). So I am basing my limited reflections on his classic work on Artificial Intelligence and human consciousness, *The Emperor's New Mind: Concerning Computers, Minds and The Laws of Physics* (1989). While acknowledging that the book is dated, it still contains relevant insights on human nature and so has become a true classic! I do not claim to understand this book, since it is very mathematical. I only want to draw some inspirations for a phenomenological approach to human consciousness.

Penrose on Consciousness

Penrose doesn't believe that computers constructed according to presently known physical principles can be intelligent and hopes that modifying quantum mechanics may be needed to explain intelligence. He holds that even "strong AI" will not be able to explain human consciousness. In this part, I base myself on John McCarthy's review of Penrose's book, which was published in 1990, one year after the publication of the book in *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society*.

The goal of AI is to understand intelligence well enough to make intelligent computer programs. It studies problems requiring intelligence for their solution and identifies and programs the intellectual mechanisms that are involved. AI has developed much more as a branch of computer science and applied mathematics than as a branch of biology. Mostly it develops, tests and makes theories about computer programs instead of making experiments and theories in psychology or neurophysiology (McCarthy, 1990). Penrose does not believe that consciousness may be explained by explorations into biology.

The most interesting and fundamental problems of AI concern trying to make programs that can achieve goals in what McCarthy calls the *common sense informatic situation*. We confront such situations in daily life and also in practising science and mathematics

Faced with these complex problems, AI has sometimes had to retreat when the limited state of the art requires it. Simplifying assumptions are made that omit important phenomena. The methodology of AI involves combinations of epistemology and heuristics. Facts are represented by

formulas of logic and other data structures, and programs manipulate these facts, sometimes by logical reasoning and sometimes by ad hoc devices.

McCarthy (1990) notes that progress in AI is made by a. Representing more kinds of general facts about the world by logical formulas or in other suitable ways. b. Identifying intellectual mechanisms, e.g. those beyond logical deduction involved in common sense reasoning. c. Representing the approximate concepts used by people in common sense reasoning. d. Devising better algorithms for searching the space of possibilities, e.g. better ways of making computers do logical deduction.

Like other sciences, AI gives rise to mathematical problems and suggests new mathematics. In the last 30 years after the publication of Penrose's book, we know that incredible progress has been made in the field of AI, with advanced robotics, driverless cars, GPS and advanced drones (Joshy 2019).

Penrose's basic conviction is that Artificial Intelligence through computers, as presently constructed, cannot in principle duplicate the workings of the human brain. His hope lies in a revised version of quantum mechanics, pioneered by Einstein, Bohn, Niels Ervin Schrödinger, etc. Penrose recalls that Einstein was in fact right to express grave philosophical doubts about quantum mechanics.

The Emperor's "new clothes," of course, were *no* clothes. The Emperor's "New Mind," we then suspect, is nothing of the sort as well (McCarthy 1990). That computers cannot possibly explain human consciousness is argued by Penrose in these terms: that all digital computers now operate according to *algorithms*, rules which the computer follows step by step. However, there are plenty of things in mathematics that *cannot* be calculated algorithmically. We can discover them and know them to be true, are using some other mode of calculation ("insight"), which not algorithmic and these are not fully understood by us. We cannot imagine that computers will also understand it, however advanced they may be.

The realist position of Penrose holds that nature of consciousness, with its attendant phenomenal objects, be part of the structure of reality and not just "a psychological adaptation in the human

species,” (McCarthy 1990). Kant’s metaphysics is certainly open to that possibility, even if it was a question that he himself did not enter into.

From Neuroscience to Revised Quantum Mechanics

So Penrose believes we must go beyond neuroscience and into the mysterious world of quantum mechanics to explain our complex mental life, including our consciousness.

In our search to understand ourselves through our consciousness, when we depend exclusively on Freud’s subconscious and other psychological theories, something seems to be missing. The philosopher David Chalmers has speculated that consciousness may be a fundamental property of nature existing outside the known laws of physics. Others claim that subjective experience is simply beyond the capacity of science to explain (Paulson, 2014).

Penrose’s theory promises a deeper level of explanation. He starts with the premise that consciousness is not computational, and it’s beyond anything that neuroscience, biology, or physics can now explain. “We need a major revolution in our understanding of the physical world in order to accommodate consciousness,” Penrose told Steve Paulson, author of *Atoms and Eden: Conversations on Religion and Science* (2010). “The most likely place, if we’re not going to go outside physics altogether, is in this big unknown – namely, making sense of quantum mechanics” (Paulson, 2014).

In another book he co-authored with Stephen Hawking, Penrose himself acknowledges: “I should think that Stephen [Hawking] plays the role of Bohr, whereas I play Einstein’s role! For Einstein argued that there should exist something like a real-world, not necessarily represented by a wave function, whereas Bohr stressed that the wave function doesn’t describe a “real” microworld but only “knowledge” that is useful for making predictions.” (Hawking and Penrose, 1996: 134-135). Though Penrose was not enamoured by the popular string theory, he did plead for revisions in quantum mechanics.

Similarly, other scientists too express this complex relationship between matter and mind. In *The Matter Myth*, by Paul Davies (a physicist in Australia) and John Gribbin (a writer who was trained in astrophysics at Cambridge), hold clearly and concisely: “[T]he reality exposed by

modern physics is fundamentally alien to the human mind, and defies all power of direct visualization” (Davies and Gribbin, 2007: 110-111). They add further, “The realization that not everything that is so in the world can be grasped by the human imagination is tremendously liberating...” (Davies and Gribbin, 2007: 110-111).

Thus starting from today’s highly sophisticated quantum mechanics Penrose pleads for a revised quantum mechanics, which alone is capable of understanding and exploring our consciousness.

Conclusion

Penrose thinks that human consciousness cannot be explored by Artificial Intelligence, however well-developed it may be. Nor by neurosciences or psychology. His hope to understand ourselves lies in a deeper and more cogent understanding of quantum mechanics, which is his own field of expertise.

In this context, the enigma of consciousness and intentionality which phenomenologists (Thomas, 2020) have been exploring is worth reaffirming. We are unique in our consciousness of ourselves. We relate to others and ourselves through intentionality. We “define” ourselves and relate to ourselves through our identity, which consists of our mind, consciousness and self-awareness. Precisely therein lie our own uniqueness and greatness. If Penrose with his highly talented mathematical brain could contribute something, that is great.

At the same time phenomenologically, we need to pay heed to the wisdom of Leo Tolstoy: “The more we live by our intellect, the less we understand the meaning of life” (Tolstoy, 1889; Pandikattu 2011). Intellect and reason, science and abstraction are crucial for human progress. We also need passion and compassion, religion and love for our collective survival, for providing value and meaning to our lives. Thus we need to be open to scientific research, philosophical quest and religious wisdom, so that we may understand the complex feature of our own consciousness and make sense of our unique lives, both individually and collectively. Our consciousness is extremely complex. So it is rich and has depth. It can pose questions, questions about our own self, meaning, freedom and existence. It can raise questions about itself! That is remarkably marvellous.

References

- Academia Europaea. n.d. "Academy of Europe: Penrose Roger." Retrieved October 11, 2020 (https://www.ae-info.org/ae/Member/Penrose_Roger).
- Davies, P. C. W., & Gribbin, J. (2007). *The matter myth: Dramatic discoveries that challenge our understanding of physical reality*. New York : Simon & Schuster
- Joshy, Divya. 2019. "Drone Technology Uses and Applications for Commercial, Industrial and Military Drones in 2020 and the Future." *Business Insider*. Retrieved October 11, 2020 (<https://www.businessinsider.in/tech/news/drone-technology-uses-and-applications-for-commercial-industrial-and-military-drones-in-2020-and-the-future/articleshow/72874958.cms>).
- McCarthy, John. (Oct 1990). *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society*, Volume 23, Number 2, October 1990, pp. 606-616.
- Pandikattu, K. (2011). *Surplus, Subversion, Submission: A Contemporary Study of Paul Ricoeur's Symbol, Metaphor and Parable*. Lambert Pub Publishing.
- Paulson, S. (2010). *Atoms and Eden: Conversations on religion and science*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Paulson, S. (May 4, 2017). "Roger Penrose On Why Consciousness Does Not Compute: The emperor of physics defends his controversial theory of mind." *Nautilus* <http://nautil.us/issue/47/consciousness/roger-penrose-on-why-consciousness-does-not-compute>
- Penrose, R. (1989) *The Emperor's New Mind: Concerning Computers, Minds and The Laws of Physics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Stephen Hawking and Roger Penrose (1996). *The Nature of Space and Time*. Princeton University Press.
- Thomas, V.C. (2020). *The Essentials of Husserl: Studies in Transcendental Phenomenology*. Wilmington: Vernon Press
- Tolstoy, L. (1889). *A Confession*. [https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/A_Confession_\(Maudes_translation\)](https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/A_Confession_(Maudes_translation))

Gargi Mukherjee is a research scholar at Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan, West Bengal. Her areas of specialisation are: post-colonial narrative, religious identity, interpretation of religious texts. Email: mantugargi@gmail.com

Article received: October 09, 2020: Accepted: October 15, 2020

© by the authors. This is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license. (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fratelli tutti (All brothers)

This third encyclical of Pope Francis, subtitled of “on fraternity and social friendship”. In the document, Francis states that the COVID-19 pandemic has proven the failure of the world to work together during the crisis. Three quotes from this Encyclical

- Of the counsels Francis offered, I would like to select the one in which he calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance, and declares blessed all those who love their brother ‘as much when he is far away from him as when he is with him.’ In his simple and direct way, St. Francis expressed the essence of a fraternal openness that allows us to acknowledge, appreciate and love each person, regardless of physical proximity, regardless of where he or she was born or lives.” (No. 1)
- “We should also recognize that destructive forms of fanaticism are at times found among religious believers, including Christians; they too “can be caught up in networks of verbal violence through the internet and the various forums of digital communication. Even in Catholic media, limits can be overstepped, defamation and slander can become commonplace, and all ethical standards and respect for the good name of others can be abandoned”. How can this contribute to the fraternity that our common Father asks of us?” (No. 46)
- “The recent pandemic enabled us to recognize and appreciate once more all those around us who, in the midst of fear, responded by putting their lives on the line. We began to realize that our lives are interwoven with and sustained by ordinary people valiantly shaping the decisive events of our shared history: doctors, nurses, pharmacists, storekeepers and supermarket workers, cleaning personnel, caretakers, transport workers, men and women working to provide essential services and public safety, volunteers, priests and religious... They understood that no one is saved alone.” (No. 54)